

Application of thermoregulation model in assessment of heat strain

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404471

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Introduction

The assessment of occupational heat strain is of great importance to human health because heat stroke usually occurs during the task. The widely used heat strain model is PHS, which has been adopted by ISO 7933 since 2004. PHS is a physiological model which is based on the heat balance equation for predicting both sweat rate and core temperature when people are in a more complex and thermal environment. However, PHS should be cautiously applied with high clothing insulation ($I_{cl} > 1\text{clo}$) or high-humidity environment^[1], possibly because thermoregulatory reactions are ignored.

Thermoregulation models include a controlled system and an active system to describe both the body temperature field and thermoregulatory responses such as vasoconstriction, vasodilation, shivering and sweating. Therefore, thermoregulation model could be a sensible method to predict body reactions. The purpose of this study is to propose a concept to evaluate heat strain combining thermoregulation model with heat strain index like PSI (Physiological Strain Index)^[2] and PeSI (Perceptual Strain Index)^[3].

Methods

Generally, the predicted core temperature, mean skin temperature and local skin temperature agree with experimental observations typically with a RMSD of 0.3, 1.0, 2.0 K, shivering and sweating response within 30W^[4]. Fiala model (suit for European), UC Berkeley model (suit for American) and Tanabe model (suit for Japanese) have been widely verified through different researches and have a good agreement.

The outputs of core temperature and thermal sensation of thermoregulation model could be as the inputs of the PSI (build on core temperature and heart rate) and PeSI (build on thermal sensation and RPE), which reflect human cardiorespiratory, thermoregulation and psychology system. Therefore, theoretical and predicted results could be responded with empirical heat indices to evaluate heat strain. The procedure is outlined schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Combination thermoregulation n model and heat strain indices

Results and discussion

Clothing factors affect the precision of thermoregulation model, including clothing thermal performance and weight. Most thermoregulation models use thermal insulation and evaporative resistance as the clothing input parameter, which may reduce 30-50% because of air and body movement. Both ISO 9920 and ISO 7933 proposed estimation methods of thermal insulation, but the correct equations are different. Specifically, dynamic insulation values consistent with ISO 9920 are lower (up to 50%) than those calculated by applying equations reported in ISO 7933 when thermal insulation is lower than 0.4 clo^[5]. Lu^[6] conducted a regression analysis of the three types of clothing and found that fabric permeability significantly affected the dynamic thermal resistance. After considering the permeability, the R² of the regression equation increased from 0.72 to 0.86. Therefore, more validations should be applied to examine the reliability of the equations and moisture accumulation within the clothing also needs to be considered.

Another clothing factor is clothing weight, and it should be taken into account when estimating the metabolic rate. Protective garments add 2.4-20.9% metabolic rate but if the weight loads on the trunk the influence will be lower.

Although the standards for human physiological limit are given in the ISO 9886:2004, the physiological tolerance of occupational people such as firefighters is underestimated. Therefore, occupational limit values of the physiological parameters of heat strain should be redefined based on a large number of human experiments.

Conclusions

Regardless of the fact that the precision of thermoregulation model is not enough within protective clothing, combination thermoregulation model and heat strain indices could be a new way to predict and evaluate heat strain. Human experiments not only can be used to verify and correct thermoregulation model, but also can build a relationship between physiological tolerance and task performance for occupational people.

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